

Study of the solution spectra of the solid Schiff base complexes in chloroform, with their limitations in solubility, has revealed a broad transition (~ 14.92 KK) for Cu (II) complex which points to a square planar geometry², may be slightly distorted due to steric reasons. In case of Ni(II) chelate, a weak broad band could be identified at ~ 14.70 KK. One broad band, under the envelope of another intense ligand absorption band, has also been observed in the short wave length region (~ 23.5 KK). The spectral profile shows more or less a tetrahedral geometry for the Ni(II) complex. Cobalt (II) does not exhibit any absorption band in the visible range suggesting thereby a tetrahedral stereochemistry. The magnetic moment values of Cu (1.73 BM), Ni (3.4 BM) and Co (5.1 BM) also indicate the above stereochemistries for the Schiff base chelates, at least in solid state.

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Coordination Behaviour of a Tetra-substituted Pyrazole: Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes with 3,4,5-Trimethyl-1-Nitroguanyl Pyrazole

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RECENTLY, a significant amount of research has centered around the transition-metal complexes of pyrazole-derived ligands¹ primarily because of the biological implications of the free ligands. As part of our programme² devoted to the study of the coordination behaviour of substituted pyrazoles, the present communication reports the synthesis of a hitherto unreported tetra-substituted pyrazole, namely, 3,4,5-trimethyl-1-nitroguanyl pyrazole (LH, Fig. 1) and its coordination behaviour by complexation with cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) salts; the solid metal complexes have been characterised from elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility measurements, electronic and vibrational spectral data.

Fig. 1

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and the solvents used were purified by usual methods.

3,4,5-Trimethyl-1-nitroguanyl pyrazole (LH) was prepared by condensation of 3-methylacetylacetone³ and nitroaminoguanidine⁴ following a method similar to that adopted by R. A. Henry⁵. The product on recrystallisation from hot ethanol gave shining white crystals, m.p. 155°. The compound is soluble in hot low molecular weight alcohols, but insoluble in water. (Found: C, 42.40; H, 5.45; N, 35.80%. $C_7H_{11}N_3O_2$ requires C, 42.60; H, 5.58; N, 35.73%).

(a) $[ML_2 \cdot nH_2O]$ [$n=0$, $M=Ni$; $n=2$; $M=Co(II)$, $Cu(II)$]: The solution obtained by mixing ethanolic solution of metalchloride hexahydrate (0.002 mole) and the ligand (0.004 mole) was adjusted to have pH 6 with dil. ammonia solution; the microcrystalline compound separated within few minutes (except the orange-red, NiL_2 which separated usually on heating over water-bath for 4-5 hours), in each case, this was filtered off,

washed with water and alcohol and finally dried over fused calcium chloride.

(b) $[\text{CoL}_2]$: This orange-yellow Co(II) complex was obtained by heating the hydrated variety, $\text{CoL}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in an air-oven at $130\text{--}140^\circ$ for 5-6 hours.

(c) $[\text{CuL}_2]$: To a solution of copper(II) chloride in ethanol (0.002 mole) was added a solution of the ligand (0.004 mole) in the same solvent. The resulting solution was left for 3-4 hours at room temperature. The resultant violet compound was collected as before.

The elemental analyses and other physico-chemical measurements like diffuse reflectance and i.r. spectra, magnetic susceptibilities and thermogravimetric analyses were carried out as described earlier².

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF THE METAL COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Found (%)		Calculated (%)		μ_{eff} (B.M.) at 295°K
		Metal	N	Metal	N	
1. $[\text{CuL}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	Light blue	12.90	28.39	12.87	28.37	2.10
2. $[\text{CuL}_2]$	Violet	14.01	30.52	13.88	30.60	1.83
3. $[\text{NiL}_2]$	Orange-red	12.98	30.84	12.96	30.92	Diamagnetic
4. $[\text{CoL}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	Light yellow	12.17	27.66	12.07	27.60	4.60
5. $[\text{CoL}_2]$	Orange yellow	13.08	30.80	13.02	30.90	4.40

Results and Discussion

The diffuse reflectance and solution (DMF) spectra, and the effective magnetic moment values of Co(II) complexes are characteristic of a high-spin octahedral configuration. The subnormal magnetic moment values may be ascribed to spin-state equilibrium between $^4\text{T}_{1g}$ and $^2\text{E}_g$ states suggesting that the overall ligand field is close to the cross-over region of $3d^7$ Co(II)⁶. The absorption bands at $8600\text{--}9600$ and $19000\text{--}20400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assignable to $^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow ^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$ (ν_1) and $^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow ^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ (ν_3) transitions respectively in an octahedral symmetry. The complex, CoL_2 , has probably a polymeric octahedral structure which might be attained through bridging nitroguanlyl group having additional donor sites of the ligand molecule.

The diamagnetic orange-red NiL_2 gives rise to a ligand field band at $21,740\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to $^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow ^1\text{A}_{2g}$ (ν_2) transition characteristic of square planar Ni(II) complex⁷⁻⁹. On dissolution in pyridine, the compound does not show any spectral change which may be ascribed either to the steric interference of the

three methyl groups in the ligand or to the strong ligand-field favouring square-planar geometry¹⁰.

The hydrated Cu(II) complex is characterised by one broad asymmetric absorption band $\sim 15300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting an octahedral structure together with low symmetry components¹¹. The effective magnetic moment and the mull spectrum of violet CuL_2 are diagnostic of a tetragonally distorted octahedral configuration. The main broad band at 18520 cm^{-1} and the shoulder at 15380 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow ^2\text{E}_g$ and $^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow ^2\text{A}_{1g}$ transitions respectively in D_{4h} symmetry^{12,13}. In pyridine solution the d-d band shifts to $\sim 14805\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating a change in stereochemistry to penta- or hexa-coordinated species by axial interaction of solvent molecules¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

In the i.r. spectra, the hydrated complexes show a medium broad band 3450 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu(\text{O-H})$ of attached water molecules coupled with $\nu(\text{N-H})$ ¹⁸. The sharp bands at 3440 and 3320 cm^{-1} in the free ligand assignable to $\nu_{asv}(\text{N-H})$ and $\nu_{sv}(\text{N-H})$ respectively¹⁹ disappeared with the appearance of a new broad band around $3350\text{--}3360\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (the broadening of the bands may be due to the inter or intra molecular interaction) in the metal complexes thereby suggesting deprotonation of one of the N-H groups in complexation forming M-N bond²⁰. The far i.r. data of NiL_2 and CoL_2 show a distinct band at $310\text{--}320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region clearly assignable to M-N (ring) stretching frequency giving positive indication of the pyrazolyl nitrogen being bonded to the metal ion. The medium sharp band at $\sim 880\text{--}885\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in hydrated complexes is characteristic of the rocking mode of coordinated water¹⁸.

TGA studies indicate that the thermal stability of the complexes follows the order $\text{NiL}_2 > \text{CuL}_2 > \text{CoL}_2$. The weight-loss percentage of the hydrated complexes at 130° corresponds to the formation of anhydrous species which finally decomposes to metal oxide within 430° .

It is reasonable to conclude that the substitution of methyl group in 4-position of the pyrazole ring, being far from the coordination sites, does not exert any significant effect on the ligational behaviour of the said compound as compared to its dimethyl analogue studied earlier².

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Electronic and I.R. Spectra of Some Transition Metal Complexes of Triazene-1-Oxides

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WHILE reviewing the studies done on the coordination complexes of triazene-1 oxides (TH) [I,II] we noted that the electronic and i.r. spectra of some transition metal complexes are not yet available in the literature. We report the relevant spectra of oxovanadium(IV), iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) chelates and some mixed chelates with dipyriddy/ *o*-phenanthroline.

Results and Discussion

A. Electronic Spectra : (i) Oxo-vanadium (IV) Complexes [VOT₂] :

Nujol mull spectra of several substituted triazene-1-oxide complexes show two well resolved bands around 16 kK and 25 kK. According to the model proposed by Ballhausen and Gray¹ these two bands are assigned to : $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ transitions. Apparently the first transition $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$ is not observed. Superimposable electronic spectra (Table I) and i.r. spectra are obtained for oxovanadium(IV) complex of

TABLE I—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) COMPLEXES OF TRIAZENE-1-OXIDE

Complex	R	Ar	Electronic Spectral bands in kK	Transitions
VOT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	16.0 26.6	$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{xz}$
VOT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃ (p)	16.1 26.0	$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{xz}$
VOT ₂	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	16.1 26.6	$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{xz}$
VOT ₂	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃ (p)	16.1 26.6	$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{xz}$

a given triazene-1-oxide irrespective of whether the complex is obtained from vanadyl sulphate or from ammonium vanadate. The first electronic transition gives the value of 10 Dq which is comparable to that (16 kK) observed for [VO(H₂O)₅]²⁺. This indicates that the ligand field strength of the bidentate triazene-1-oxides is comparable to that of H₂O—a conclusion arrived at by Behera and Chakravorty² from a comparison of the electronic spectra of [Cr(H₂O)₆]³⁺ (10 Dq=17.4 kK) and [CrT₃] (R=alkyl, Ar=aryl) (10 Dq=17.4 kK).

(ii) Mixed Chelates of Cobalt(II) [CoT₂.dipy/ *o*-phen] :

The electronic spectra of two mixed chelates of cobalt(II) containing two 1,3-diphenyl triazene-1-oxides and one dipy/ *o*-phen were run in nujol mull as well as in acetone solution. Unfortunately only one high energy absorption band around 25 kK and one broad and weak band centered around 10.5 kK could be detected. Besides, some slight structures are observed around 16.5-18.0 kK. The low energy transition around 10 kK may be assigned to ν_1 (${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$) while the second may be ν_2 (${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$). Introduction of strong field